

solvent distilled off to get the respective unsaturated ester in good yield.

A mixture of the unsaturated esters (0.1 mol) in methanol (20 dm³) and aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (10% ; 80 dm³) was refluxed for 8 h. After cooling, the unreacted ester was extracted with ether, and the separated aqueous layer was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the residue filtered to obtain the required acids in 60–67% yield.

Preparation of the amides (1, 2): To a well-stirred solution of the respective acid (10 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (50 dm³) at 0° containing triethylamine (5 mmol) and the appropriate amine (10 mmol) was added a solution of phosphorus oxychloride (10 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 dm³). Additional triethylamine (7 mmol) was added to it in one instalment. The contents were stirred for 0.5 h at 0° and continued stirring for further 6 h at room temperature. Progress of the reaction was studied by tlc at regular intervals. The excess reagents were decomposed by pouring it on crushed ice and the organic layer was extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 dm³). The organic extract was washed with 10% aqueous sodium carbonate solution (to remove unreacted acid) followed by water, 10% HCl (to separate unreacted amine) and finally with water. After drying over anhydrous calcium chloride, the solvent was evaporated. The residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and chloroform mixture (3 : 2) as eluent to get the amide.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of 1-Aroyl-5-(p-sulphamylphenylazo)-3,4-dimethylpyrano[2,3-c]pyrazol-6(1H)-ones

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PYRAZOLES are found to possess various biological activities¹. Here, we report the synthesis of the title compounds and evaluate their biological activities. The synthesis involved the condensation

of substituted-arylhya-zines with ethylacetoacetate in dioxane to give 2-ethyl butyrate-2-substituted-arylhya-zones (1). 1 underwent cyclodehydration with o-dichlorobenzene to give 3-methyl-(1-substituted-aryyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2) in good yields (Scheme 1). The pyrazolones (2) formed were the mixture of keto and enol forms, explained on the basis of nmr spectral (taken in TFA) studies. In most of the cases, a two-proton signal at δ 2.5 and another at δ 5–6 depending upon the structure, were observed. The enol form is stabilised by the keto group at aroyl/aryloxy substituent at N₁-position of pyrazolone. Here, the formation of 3a–q from 2a–q occurs through the intermediacy of 2a–q and it is the enol form which is responsible for further reactions. The compounds have been characterised by the observation of ir band at 1740 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl), and two pmr signals at δ 2.3 (C₃-methyl) and 2.45 (C₄-methyl).

Scheme 1

Biological activity: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity using cup-plate agar diffusion technique² against gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas pyocyanea* at 25 and 50 µg ml⁻¹ concentrations using tetracycline as a standard.

The compounds were also tested for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* using agar-plate method³ with Dithan M-45 as a standard commercial fungicide at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations. The data indicate that the presence of sulphamyl moiety plays key role in the fungitoxicity of the compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as an internal reference.

Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates using iodine as chromogen.

The following procedure forms a general method for the synthesis of compounds 1-4 (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF ARYL/ARYLOXY-PYRAZOLONES (2)*, PYRANOPYRAZOLES (3) AND SULPHAMYLPHENYLAZOPYRAZOLES (4)*

Compd. no	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C
2a	p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃	199
2b	p-OH, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	260
2c	o-CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃	185
2d	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃	220
2e	o-OH, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃	270
2f	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄	210
2g	p-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃	140
2h	o-CH ₃ , OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	75
2i	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃	125
2j	C ₆ H ₅ , OH=CH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	195
2k	o-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	193
2l	o-Cl, C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	195
2m	C ₆ H ₅ , O CH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	94
2n	2,4-(OH) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ , O.OH	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃	225
2o	p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	230
2p	o-Cl, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	177
2q	p-Cl, m-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	110
3a	p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	230
3b	p-CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃	170
3c	o-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃	175
3d	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	215
3e	o-OH, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃	190
3f	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄	192
3g	p-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃	85
3h	C ₆ H ₅ , OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	218
3i	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃	110
3j	C ₆ H ₅ , OH=CH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	298
3k	o-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	210
3l	o-Cl, C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	220
3m	C ₆ H ₅ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	98
3n	2,4-(OH) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄	222
3o	p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	225
3p	o-Cl, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	192
3q	p-Cl, m-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	232
4a	p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄ S	185
4b	p-OH, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ S	183
4c	o-CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ S	155
4d	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ S	235
4e	o-OH, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄ S	80
4f	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₁₀ N ₅ S	90
4g	p-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ S	80
4h	C ₆ H ₅ , OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ S	225
4i	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₇ N ₄ S	210
4j	C ₆ H ₅ , OH=CH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ S	190
4k	o-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ S	198
4l	o-Cl, C ₆ H ₄ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ ClS	175
4m	C ₆ H ₅ , O OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ S	78
4n	2,4-(OH) ₂ , C ₆ H ₃ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₁₀ N ₅ S	232
4o	p-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ S	182
4p	o-Cl, C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄ ClS	204
4q	p-Cl, m-OH, C ₆ H ₄ , O.OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₄ ClS	210

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Ethyl butyrate-2-aryloxyhydrazones (1a): To a solution of the aroyl hydrazine (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) in dioxane (20 ml), ethyl acetoacetate (0.65 g, 0.005 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed gently for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue poured into ice-cold water.

The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 1a, m.p. 110°, C₁₅H₁₅O₄N₃; $\nu_{\max}$ 1700 (C=O, ester), 1600 (C=N) and 1050 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 1.19 (3H, t, CH₃, ester), 2.15 (3H, s, N=CCH₃), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH₂, ester), 6.8-7.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH exchangeable with D₂O).

N₁-Aroyl/aryloxy acetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (2a): A solution of 1a (3.02 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in *o*-dichlorobenzene (20 ml) for about 5 h and then kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 2a, m.p. 192°, C₁₁H₉O₄N₃; $\nu_{\max}$ 1670 (CON), 1580 (C=N) and 1050 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 2.15 (3H, s, N=CCH₃), 2.55 (2H, s, CH₂CO cyclic), 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic), 7-7.5 (4H, m, Ar), 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic), 7-7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 15.0 (1H, s br, OH enolic).

N₁-Aroyl-3,4-dimethylpyrano[2,3-c]pyrazol-6-(1H)-one (3a): A mixture of 2a (2.47 g, 0.01 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (2.6 g, 0.02 mol) was heated on an oil-bath at 160° for about 2 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from dioxane to give 3a, m.p. 230°, C₁₅H₁₁O₅N₃; $\nu_{\max}$ 1740 (CO-O lactone), 1580 (C=N) and 1060 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 2.3 (3H, s, C₃-CH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 6.0 (1H, s, olefinic proton) and 6.8-7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

1-Aroyl-5-(p-sulphamylphenylazo)-3,4-dimethylpyrano[2,3-c]pyrazol-6(1H)-ones (4a): A solution of 3a (3.91 g, 0.012 mol) was added diazotised solution of sulphanilamide (1.725 g, 0.0125 mol) containing sodium acetate (0.8 g) and stirred vigorously and then kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised to furnish 4a, m.p. 185°, C₂₁H₁₆O₇N₆S; $\nu_{\max}$ 3240 (NH), 1740 (CO-O), 1580 (=C=N), 1580 (N=N) and 1050 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 2.3 (3H, s, C₃-CH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃) and 8.2 (1H, s br, SO₂HN).

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